

APPENDIX for

Quality information Document (QUID)
for the validation of the Copernicus Marine
reanalysis product of the Mediterranean
biogeochemistry

MEDSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_BGC_006_014

v3.4

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Appendix A: class 1 climatological comparison

This appendix provides supplementary information and additional context to support and enhance the content presented in the Quality Information Document (QUID) for the validation of the Copernicus Marine Analysis and Forecast product of the Mediterranean biogeochemistry (<https://documentation.marine.copernicus.eu/QUID/CMEMS-MED-QUID-006-014.pdf>).

This Appendix reports the Class 1 visual comparison for selected model variables. Weekly (grey lines) and overall average (black lines) profiles for the model run 2022-2024 are compared with climatological vertical profiles (red dots for means and dashed lines for standard deviations) for 16 sub-basins of the Mediterranean Sea (as listed in the QUID document). Two sets of figures are shown: one for oxygen and nutrient variables (Figure A.1), and one for carbonate system variables (Figure A.2). The adr1 sub-basin was excluded due to the limited area corresponding to the open sea (for definition, below 200 m depth). Climatologies are build considering in-situ observations of the 1999-2023 period present in the MedBGCins-v1 dataset (as described in the QUID document).

Figure A.1. Comparison between weekly (grey lines) and annual (black lines) vertical profiles from the Copernicus Marine model run for the Mediterranean sub-basins (except adr1) and climatological profiles of nitrate, phosphate, dissolved oxygen, silicate and ammonium retrieved from MedBGCins-v1 dataset (red dots) in open sea areas.

Figure A.1. (cont). See above.

Figure A.1. (cont). See above.

Figure A.1 (cont.). See above.

Figure A.2. Profiles of pCO₂, DIC, ALK and pH in total scale: mean weekly model profiles (grey colour lines; from January to December 2019), mean annual model profiles (black lines) and derived climatological (\pm standard deviation) profiles (red dots and dashed lines) for the sub-basins of Figure III.1 (except adr1) in open sea areas.

Figure A.2. (cont.) See above.

Figure A.2. (cont.) See above.

Figure A.2. (cont.) See above.